

Application of Bunnett Criterion in Mixed Aqueous Solvents

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The present paper shows that the application of Bunnett criterion to mechanistic investigations in mixed aqueous organic media is limited and that caution must be exercised in interpreting kinetic data in such media.

An important aspect of the application of Bunnett's criteria to the mechanistic investigations of acid catalysed reactions is that they have been applied¹ only to reactions in aqueous solutions. Recently an attempt was made² to apply these criteria to the acid catalysed hydrolysis of a few organic substrates in glycerol-water mixtures. Because of the well known advantages of mixed aqueous organic media^{3,4,5} in kinetic investigations of this nature, this work deals with an extension of these measurements to reactions proceeding by different mechanistic paths and the results are discussed.

The reactions chosen were (a) the iodination of acetone and (b) the hydrolysis of dimethoxymethane and have been studied in the composition range 10–50% by weight of glycerol. The hydrolysis of dimethoxymethane was also studied at higher compositions in glycerol to understand the effect of solvent on the rate of this reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Both these reactions have fairly measurable rates under the low acid concentrations necessitated by the conditions of the experiment and for which the mechanisms are also reasonably established from other evidence³. All the chemicals used were purified according to standard methods. All solutions were prepared and standardised where necessary, according to the recommended methods.

(a) *Iodination of acetone* : The reaction was followed in a Hilger Spekker absorptiometer at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Details of the method of measurement are found elsewhere⁵. The reaction was found to be zero order with respect to iodine and good zero order plots were obtained in the glycerol-water mixtures. The results are presented in Table 1 and the zero order rate constants were calculated from the slopes of the above mentioned graphs and converted into the proper units. The activity of water in these mixtures was computed from

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3. M. A. Paul and F. A. Long, *Chem. Revs.*, 1957, **57**, 935.
4. C. A. Bunton, J. B. Ley, A. J. Rhind-Tutt and C. A. Vernon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2327.
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the osmotic coefficient data of Hamer *et al.*⁶. A graph of the logarithm of the zero order rate constant against water activity in these media was drawn and is shown in figure 1. The slope of this graph is -4.4 and is designated w_g .*

FIG. 1. IODINATION OF ACETONE IN GLYCEROL-WATER MIXTURES. PLOT OF $5 + \log \frac{K_0}{C_0^0}$ AGAINST $-\log a_{H_2O}$.

TABLE 1

Overall concentration of acetone $0.1070 M$
 Overall concentration of HCl $0.0107 M$
 Overall concentration of iodine $10^{-4} M$

Solvent composition wt. % glycerol	Rate constant in moles litre ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
10	1.55×10^{-6}
25	1.98×10^{-6}
40	2.53×10^{-6}
50	3.62×10^{-6}
60	4.17×10^{-6}

(b) *Hydrolysis of dimethoxymethane*: The reaction was followed by a dilatometric method at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$. The pseudo first order rate constants were calculated from the graphs of $\log(v_\infty - v_t)$ against time. Table 2 gives the best values of the rate constants in different glycerol-water mixtures, as also H_0 data obtained in these mixtures using *p*-nitroaniline as indicator. Figure 2 shows the variation of rate with the composition at the acid concentration maintained in the kinetic experiments.

FIG. 2. HYDROLYSIS OF METHYLAL-VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT (CURVE 1) AND H_0 (CURVE 2) WITH SOLVENT COMPOSITION.

TABLE 2

Overall concentration of dimethoxymethane 0.18 *M*
 Overall concentration of HCl 0.010 *M*

Solvent composition wt. % of glycerol	Rate constant min ⁻¹	H ₀
0	0.02 × 10 ⁻³ *	1.99
10	5.32 × 10 ⁻³	1.74
30	3.93 × 10 ⁻³	1.94
40	3.56 × 10 ⁻³	2.12
50	5.68 × 10 ⁻³	2.32
70	1.4 × 10 ⁻²	1.96
90	1.63 × 10 ⁻²	1.63

* Ref. 7.

(a) *Discussion* : Iodination of acetone.

The slope w_g^* of the Bunnett plot for this reaction in these media is -4.4 and the slope for the corresponding reaction with the same plot in aqueous media is w^* .—Schaleger *et al.*² compared their w_g (actually they are w_g^*) values with the w values of aqueous media (and not with w^*).

Our arguments are based on a comparison of w_g^* values obtained in these media with the w^* values of aqueous media. According to Bunnett's classification¹ reactions with w^* values less than -2 involve the reaction of water molecule as a nucleophile in the rate determining step, while reactions with w^* values greater than -2 involve the role of water as a proton transfer agent. In this analysis w^* is interpreted as a difference in the hydration of the transition state to that of substrate and proton. The importance of the relative hydration of the different species including the transition state involved in the reaction has been emphasised in recent communications.^{8,9}

A significant aspect of our results is the fact that the magnitude of w_g^* is considerably outside the limit suggested by Bunnett for a reaction of this type in which water acts as a proton transfer agent. Actually the slope of this reaction indicates that water acts as a nucleophile which is contrary to the fairly established role¹⁰ of water as a base in the rate determining step of this reaction. This clearly shows that the Bunnett criterion also suffers from certain drawbacks. From our results it is only possible to say whether water is involved in the rate determining stage or not but no information can be given regarding its function.

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It is also noted that the rate of iodination increases considerably with increasing glycerol content of the medium. This result is not surprising¹¹ in view of the fact that the rate determining stage of the reaction involves an ion and a dipolar molecule. Similar observations have been made^{5,12} for this reaction in other alcohol-water mixtures. It has been suggested⁸ that rationalisation of solvent effects in kinetic investigations on the basis of electrostatic considerations is not always satisfactory. Our results on this reaction show that although this may be true of A-1 reactions, it cannot be generalised in the case of A-2 reactions.

(b) *Hydrolysis of dimethoxymethane* : It is seen from Table 2 that the rate of hydrolysis of dimethoxymethane increases considerably with the addition of glycerol upto about 10% and then decreases, until a composition of about 50% by weight of glycerol, is reached and then increases with further additions of glycerol. These results are not in agreement with the observations of Schaleger *et al.*² on the hydrolysis of some ketals, but are in general accord with the results in other media such as ethanol¹³, dioxan¹⁴, acetone¹⁵ and dimethylformamide¹⁶, the only difference being the initial increase in rate upto 10% by weight of glycerol noted in our experiments. The variation in the rate of this reaction closely follows the changes in the H_0 acidity measure in the different compositions as seen from Table 2. It is plausible, therefore, to expect from these results that the rate change is associated with the change of acidity of the medium. The observed changes in rate could arise due to two competing factors both of which affect the indicator acidity (1) shift of the equilibrium

to the right and (2) changes in the activity coefficient of the hydronium ion with the dielectric constant of the medium on the addition of glycerol to an aqueous solution of an acid.

Our results show that there is no simple relationship between the rate constant and the activity of water in these media. This is to be expected for there is considerable evidence for this reaction to indicate that water is not involved in the rate determining stage of the reaction. For such reactions no w^* values were quoted by Bunnett but at higher acidities a value of -2.5 is reported.

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